

It can be inferred that the minima in $\Delta\bar{V}_{tr}^\ddagger$ values correspond to the region where solute-solvent interactions are maximum.

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Oxidation Products of Taraxasteryl Acetate and Molecular Rearrangement of its Epoxide

U. K. SOM, A. K. SIL, K. E. HAQUE and C. P. DUTTA*

Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani, Kalyani-741 235

and

K. P. DHARA

Department of Chemistry, University College of Science, 92 A. P. C. Road, Calcutta-700 009

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A number of interesting molecular rearrangements as a result of epoxide ring opening has been reported in recent years¹. In continuation of our investigation^{2,3} on the molecular rearrangement involving epoxide ring opening in pentacyclic triterpenoid skeleton taraxa-20 α ,30 α -oxido-3 β -yl acetate (2) was prepared by the action of *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid⁴ on taraxasteryl acetate (1). During epoxidation two other products were also isolated which are believed to be formed through the intermediacy of 2. The α -orientation of epoxy function in 2, m.p. 274-75°, [α]_D+102° (CHCl₃), was justifiable from both ¹H nmr studies and stereochemical viewpoint, C₂₀-C₃₀ bond now being favourably β -oriented.

The structure of the major rearranged product obtained during the aforesaid reaction was proposed as 3. The compound 3, C₃₂H₅₂O₄ (M⁺ 500), m.p. 232° [α]_D+2.07 (EtOH) was shown to possess an enlarged E-ring bearing keto carbonyl and hydroxyl functionalities (1 715 and 3 400 cm⁻¹, respectively). The acetate carbonyl appeared at 1 720 cm⁻¹ as one of the twin peaks. In the ¹H nmr spectrum a signal at δ 3.45 (1H, m) was assigned to methine proton at C₂₀-bearing OH group. A two-proton broad signal was discernible at δ 3.70 which turned into a one-proton singlet on deuteration. This signal was attributed to C₂₀-proton and C₂₀-hydroxylic proton, the latter would disappear after the treatment with deuterium oxide. The other methylenes, methylene and methine protons resonated at their usual regions. The mass fragmentation pattern (Chart 1) of the compound was in conformity with the structure proposed and as rationalised for taraxastane class of triterpenoids⁵.

The minor component 4, C₃₂H₅₀O₃ (M⁺ 482) m.p. 215°, [α]_D+3.7° (EtOH), showed λ_{max} 220 nm (ϵ 6000) accounting for the presence of an α,β -unsaturated keto group in the molecule. Occurrence of an infrared absorption peak at 1 695 cm⁻¹ along with the one at 1 720 cm⁻¹ (acetate carbonyl) also suggested the above conjecture. From mechanistic consideration and appearance of a one-proton multiplet at δ 6.66 it led to the structure 4 which essentially originated from 3 by the loss of one molecule of H₂O. The assignment of structure 4 was

Chart 1

further corroborated from its mass fragmentation pattern which was very similar to that observed for 3.

Treatment of the epoxide (2) with anhydrous SnCl_4 in dry benzene at room temperature yielded two isomeric products having molecular formula $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_3$ (M^+ 484). The less polar one was characterised as taraxa-30-al-3 β -yl acetate (5), m.p. 202–04°, $[\alpha]_D + 0^\circ$; $\nu_{\max}$ 1720 and 1725 cm^{-1} . Its ^1H nmr spectrum showed a singlet at δ 9.54 (1H, s) attributable to the aldehydic proton at C_{30} , the remaining part of the spectrum being conformity with the structure (5)⁸.

The more polar compound, m.p. 255–58°, $\nu_{\max}$ 1700 and 1725 cm^{-1} , was identified as compound (6)⁸ where an enlargement of ring-E had taken place by means of ^1H nmr and mass spectral analysis. Treatment of the epoxide with BBr_3 in dry benzene at room temperature furnished a compound (7), $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_3$ (M^+ 484) m.p. 290–92° $[\alpha]_D + 96^\circ$ (CHCl_3), which was identified as taraxa-21-oxo-3 β -yl acetate from spectral measurements and comparison studies^{3,8}.

Experimental

All m.p.s. are uncorrected. Petroleum ether used had b.p. 60–80°. Tlc was carried out on silica gel G plates and column chromatography with silica gel of 60–100 mesh. All the organic extracts were dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Pmr

spectra (60 and 100 MHz) were recorded in CDCl_3 with TMS as internal standard. Uv spectrum was recorded in a Beckman DB-G spectrophotometer.

Taraxasterol (m.p. 216–18°), isolated in large quantities from the petroleum ether extract of *Cirsium arvense*, on treatment with acetic anhydride (20 ml) in pyridine (20 ml) for 3 h at room temperature followed by the usual workup after keeping overnight, furnished a solid which was chromatographed over silica gel and crystallised from chloroform–methanol to give taraxasteryl acetate as white silky solid, m.p. 248–50°, $[\alpha]_D + 102^\circ$ [lit.⁹, m.p. 255–56°; $[\alpha]_D + 101^\circ$ (CHCl_3)].

Taraxa-20 α ,30 α -oxido-3 β -yl acetate (2): A solution of 1 (0.8 g) and *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid (0.8 g) in chloroform (50 ml) was allowed to stand at 0° for 2 h with occasional shaking. The usual workup furnished a solid showing five spots on tlc. The solid was chromatographed over a column of silica gel (14 g). The first compound (0.120 g) coming down on elution with petroleum ether–benzene (9 : 1) on crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform–methanol gave pure crystals of taraxa-20 α ,30 α -oxido-3 β -yl acetate (2), m.p. 274–75°, M^+ 484 (Found : C, 79.55; H, 10.64. $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_3$ requires : C, 79.34; H, 10.74%); $[\alpha]_D + 102^\circ$ (CHCl_3); m/z 484 (M^+), 424, 408, 249, 205 and 189 (100%).

On elution of the column with petroleum ether–benzene (65 : 35) gave a white solid whose tlc showed the presence of two compounds. So these fractions were subjected to re-chromatography.

Oxidation products of taraxasteryl acetate (1): The less polar component of the re-chromatogram obtained after elution of the column with petroleum ether–benzene (56 : 44) was crystallised from chloroform–methanol. Compound 4 was obtained as pure crystals, m.p. 215°, M^+ 482 (Found : C, 79.49; H, 10.35. $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_3$ requires : C, 79.62; H, 10.44%); m/z 482 (M^+), 422, 407, 259, 189 (100%) 137, 107 and 95.

The more polar compound (m.p. 229–230°) from the chromatogram, obtained after elution with petroleum ether–benzene (5 : 6) on crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform–methanol yielded pure crystals of compound 3, m.p. 232–33° (M^+ 500) (Found : C, 76.52; H, 10.35. $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_4$ requires : C, 76.75; H, 10.47%); m/z 500 (M^+), 482 ($M^+ - 18$), 440 ($M^+ - 60$), 422 ($M^+ - (60 - 18)$), 407, 249, 203, 189 (100%), 137 and 95.

Action of anhydrous SnCl_4 on the epoxide (2). Formation of taraxa-30-al-3 β -yl acetate (5) and the E-ring enlarged product (6): The epoxide (2; 0.1 g) was treated with anhydrous SnCl_4 (0.2 ml) in dry benzene (15 ml) and the mixture was stirred for 30 min at room temperature. The usual workup furnished a crude mass, which upon chromatographic separation over silica gel furnished 5 (20 g), m.p. 202–04°, $[\alpha]_D \pm 0^\circ$, and 6 (70 mg), m.p. 250–52°.

Treatment of the epoxide (2) with BBr_3 . Formation of taraxa-21-oxo-3 β -yl acetate (7): The epoxide (2; 0.1 g) was treated with BBr_3 (0.2 ml) in dry benzene (15 ml) and the mixture was stirred for 30 min at room temperature. The usual work up furnished a solid (7), m.p. 290–92° [α]_D+102° ($CHCl_3$).

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Studies on 1,3,4-Oxadiazoles. Part-IX†. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of 2-Phenyl-5-*p*-(2',4'-bis-ethylamino-s-triazin-6'-ylaminophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles

C. L. PATEL and HANSA PAREKH*

Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University,
Rajkot-360 005

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SOME s-triazine and 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives have found important biological application^{1,2}. With a view to get better therapeutic activity, we have synthesised³ compounds of type 4 containing

† Part-VIII; See Ref. 8.

both the said moieties and screened them for their antimicrobial activity.

Cyanuric chloride¹ (0.1 mol, 18.4 g) was condensed with ethylamine (0.2 mol, 9.8 g) to get 2,4-bis-ethylamino-6-chloro-s-triazine (1). The third chlorine atom of cyanuric chloride was replaced by ethyl-*p*-aminobenzoate to get the triazine (2) which was further treated with hydrazine hydrate to obtain the hydrazide (3). The hydrazide (3) was then condensed with different aromatic acids in the presence of phosphorus oxychloride to obtain the 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives (4). The structure of the products has been characterised by ir spectral study.

- 1; X=Cl
2; X=NHC₆H₄CO₂Et (*p*)
3; X=NHC₆H₄CONHNH₂ (*p*)

4

Antimicrobial activity: The compounds were screened for antibacterial and antifungal activity using cup-plate method⁴. The testing was carried out at a concentration of 50 μ g using gram-positive bacteria, i.e. *Staphylococcus aureus* and *S. citreus*, gram-negative bacteria, i.e. *Escherichia coli* and *Marcasne serratia*, and fungi, i.e. *Aspergillus niger* and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. It was observed that most of the compounds were moderately active (16–24 mm zone of inhibition) against different strains of bacteria and fungi.

However, comparatively significant activity was observed in compounds bearing (in parenthesis zone of inhibition, mm) R=phenyl (15–19), styryl (14–24), 3-chlorophenyl (14–23), 3-hydroxyphenyl (15–20), 2,4-dihydroxyphenyl (13–24) and 3-pyridinyl (14–19).

Experimental

All the melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The ir spectra (KBr) was taken on a Shimadzu DR-1, 435-IR spectrophotometer in the range 4 000–400 cm^{-1} .

Ethyl(2,4-bis-ethylamino-s-triazin-6-yl)aminobenzoate (2): A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol, 2.02 g) and ethyl *p*-aminobenzoate (0.01 mol, 1.7 g) in dioxane (10 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for 2 h. The product was isolated and crystallised from dioxane,